

Tephrosia fallow enhances grain yield of maize-common bean intercrops: Results from a demonstration trial in western Kenya

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Abstract

In Early 2018, a stakeholders' workshop sponsored by DIVERSify Horizon 2020 project was held at the Lake Victoria Basin Eco-region Research Programme (LVBERP) Maseno Centre to identify tacit knowledge, local innovations, strategies and farmer best practice on cropping systems. In Nyabeda village of Siaya County, Western Kenya, improved fallows is the most widely used cropping system, and local farmers practice various forms of the technology to suit their needs. Improved fallows involve the planting of fast-growing fallow species as part of a crop-fallow rotation for rapid replenishment of soil fertility - usually selected for their nitrogen-fixing abilities and green manure to support the predominantly maize (*Zea mays*) and common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) intercropping systems. A demonstration trial was established in Nyabeda Primary School (0°07'N, 34°24'E, 1330 metres above sea level). The trial, which also doubled as an experimental Case Study for TRUE Horizon 2020 project, was carried out during the short rains between September and December 2018, and the long rains between March and July 2019. The experiment tested both simultaneous and sequential agroforestry fallow technologies. The experimental design was informed by the various local farming practices, incorporating - the tephrosia (*Tephrosia candida*) improved fallow technology in maize-bean intercrops. Nyabeda receives mean annual rainfall of 1500–1900 mm and annual temperature of 22°C to 24°C. The soil at the site is silty clay loam, classified as Ferralsol with low pH and nitrogen (N). The trial had a split-plot design with treatments: (i) monocultures of maize, common beans and tephrosia, (ii) mixtures of maize+common beans, maize+tephrosia, tephrosia+common beans and maize+common beans+tephrosia. Mixed species treatments were established by planting alternate rows of 266,667 plants/ha for common beans, and 61,538 plants ha⁻¹ for maize and tephrosia. Other treatments were rhizobial inoculation and inorganic fertiliser application at the rate of 123.5 kg ha⁻¹ of DAP/NPK, including treatments with no inoculation and fertiliser application as controls. After harvesting the short rains crop, tephrosia green manure (foliage and pods) was uniformly spread and incorporated back into their respective plots, then planted with maize and beans – singly or as intercrops in the long rains (second season). Tephrosia green manure increased maize yields (8,772 kg ha⁻¹) in the subsequent long rains season compared with sole maize receiving inorganic fertiliser (7,726 kg ha⁻¹), while common bean yield after tephrosia green manure (3,311 kg ha⁻¹) was not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from sole common bean receiving inorganic fertiliser (3,863 kg ha⁻¹). Overall, the maize and bean grain yields, including those of maize and bean intercrops were generally higher than the reported average yields for the region.

In addition, use of tephrosia fallow and intercrop reduced the incidence of the parasitic witchweed (*Striga hermonthica*) on maize. We recommend that smallholder farmers use both simultaneous and sequential tephrosia fallow systems in consecutive seasons.

Key words: Common bean, improved fallow, intercropping, maize, rhizobial inoculation, tephrosia

Introduction

One of the most critical constraints to food security in sub-Saharan Africa is declining soil fertility, especially for the vast majority smallholder farmers who grow crops continuously with minimal nutrient inputs. Therefore, improving soil fertility using sustainable agricultural systems is paramount in achieving the food security agenda in the region (Partey *et al.*, 2020). Various agroforestry-based production systems developed in the past 40 years have been integrated into the farming systems in various forms and conditions. In most cases, farmers have modified the initial researcher-modelled to farmer-modified systems to address the various socioeconomic and ecological challenges they are facing today, including those brought about by the climate change. Our study region has been at the centre of innovations of agroforestry-related soil fertility enhancement technologies for the production of the staple food crops-maize (*Zea mays*) and common beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*).

In Early 2018, a stakeholders' workshop was held at the Kenya Forestry Research Institute's Lake Victoria Basin Eco-region Research Programme (LVBERP) Maseno Centre to identify tacit knowledge, local innovations, strategies and farmer best practice on cropping systems. In this workshop, the stakeholders- comprising farmers, breeders, community based organisations and extension workers listed several technologies and own innovations being practised in the region, namely improved fallows, biomass transfer, mixed cropping /rotational intercropping, integrated soil fertility management and 'push and pull' (Sanchez, 1999; Midega *et al.*, 2018). In Nyabeda, Western Kenya tephrosia improved fallows is one of the main agroforestry technologies used in maize and common bean cropping systems and the local farmers practice various forms of the technology to suit their needs. Improved fallows involve the planting of fast-growing fallow species as part of a crop-fallow rotation for rapid replenishment of soil fertility – usually selected for their nitrogen-fixing abilities. Improved fallows may involve the use of herbaceous legumes (e.g. clovers, *Trifolium* spp.), also commonly known as green manures or cover crops, while woody legumes are usually referred to by the tree or shrub species used (Sanchez, 1999). In the latter case, the term 'improved' also has the connotation that it is short duration fallow species, lasting no more than a season, and can be established as an intercrop with the target companion crop (e.g. maize or beans) in the first season, while the leafy biomass produced is returned as green manure for crops in the following season(s). Here, we report the preliminary findings of field trial established to determine the impact of tephrosia improved fallow green manure, inorganic fertiliser, legume rhizobial inoculation and various crop combinations (as monocrops or intercrops) and on yields of maize and common bean. The trial was co-designed with the local farmers with the aim to include the various forms of maize, bean and tephrosia combinations and inorganic fertiliser inputs.

Materials and Methods

Site description

The experiments were carried out at Nyabeda primary School -Siaya County, Kenya (0°07'N, 34°24'E, 1,330 m above sea level). The site is located in the sub-humid agro-climatic zone. The annual mean temperature is 22°C–24°C with a bimodal mean annual rainfall of 1500–1800 mm

over two cropping seasons; the long rains (LR) occurring between March and July, and the short rains (SR) between September and December. The soil at the site is silty clay loam, classified as Ferralsol and has the following physicochemical properties: pH, 5.9; total soil organic carbon (SOC, %), 1.35; total nitrogen (N%), 0.12; P (mg P kg⁻¹), 2.99; Ca (cmolc kg⁻¹), 1.68, and extractable K (me 100 g⁻¹), 1.68. Maize and beans are the main staple crops and are grown as either a monocrop or intercrops. Farm sizes are predominantly smallholdings, ranging from 1–3 ha (Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, MoALF, 2016).

Experimental design

The design and treatments were informed by the various local farming practices, incorporating - the tephrosia (*Tephrosia candida*) improved fallow technology to enhance maize (*Zea mays*) and common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) production. Local farmers participated in the management and assessment of the trial. The experiment was laid out in split-split plot design. The treatment blocks were (i) legume rhizobial inoculation (inoculated and non-inoculated), where a legume (tephrosia or common bean) was planted either as sole or intercrop, and (i) two fertiliser levels (0 and 120 kg ha⁻¹). The study was conducted in two consecutive cropping seasons on the same plot; the short rains season (SR) from October 2019–February 2019 and the long rains season (LR) from May–September 2020. The fallow species was tephrosia (*Tephrosia candida*) planted during the first season- SR. The plants were established either as monocultures of maize, common beans and tephrosia (hereafter referred to as ‘sole’), or mixtures of maize + common bean, maize+ tephrosia, tephrosia+common bean and maize + common bean + tephrosia. Each plot was 20 m². The planting densities were 266,667 plants ha⁻¹ for common beans, and 61,538 plants ha⁻¹ for maize and tephrosia. The legumes- tephrosia and common bean were inoculated with specific rhizobial inoculants. Plots comprising non-inoculated tephrosia and common bean were included as controls to evaluate the effect of rhizobia inoculation. Each treatment (plant species single or mixtures × rhizobial inoculation × fertiliser application) was replicated three times. After harvesting, the SR crops (January 2019) tephrosia plants were cut back and the aboveground biomass was separated into wood, foliage, pods, and litterfall, the woody material was removed. The remainder (green manure) was uniformly spread over the respective plots prior to the second season (long rains) planting in 2019 with common beans and maize, either as sole crops or as intercrop mixtures.

Results

Tephrosia green biomass yields during the SR ranged from 900–8,500 kg ha⁻¹ assessed 6 months after planting. Rhizobial inoculation significantly increased the leafy biomass of tephrosia ($P < 0.05$). The lowest yield was obtained in uninoculated tephrosia with fertiliser application. On the other hand, the highest yield was obtained in rhizobia-inoculated tephrosia receiving inorganic fertiliser.

The results presented in Table 1 showed that rhizobial inoculation and fertiliser application had no significant effects on bean grain yields in both seasons. However, bean grain yields were higher during the long rains (2,123–2,377 kg ha⁻¹) than short rains (499–669 kg ha⁻¹). As expected, bean grain yield was significantly higher in sole bean crop than bean intercrops with maize, tephrosia or both. The highest bean grain yield (3,864 kg ha⁻¹) was produced with sole bean plots; there was no significant difference in bean grain yields between sole bean with fertilisation and sole bean grown on the short rains tephrosia green manure-bean intercrop plots.

As with bean crop, the maize grain yields were higher during the long rains than the short rains (Table 2). The highest maize grain yield (8,772 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained with sole maize grown on sole tephrosia green manure plots from the short rains. However, the yields were also comparable with intercrops (maize + tephrosia, maize + bean + tephrosia) and sole maize. Inoculation of bean and tephrosia, and fertilisation did not have any significant effect on maize grain yields.

Table 1. Common bean grain yields in different treatments (*Rhizobium* inoculation-bean & tephrosia, inorganic and organic fertiliser and plant combination) during two consecutive cropping seasons (short and long rains) in Nyabeda, Western Kenya. Means within a treatment factor not followed by the same letter (s) in a column are significantly different at $P=0.05$ according to Fischer least significance difference (LSD); NA, not applicable

Treatment	Mean Bean yields (Kg ha ⁻¹) Short Rains	Mean Bean yields (Kg ha ⁻¹) Long Rains
Inoculation		
With	499a	2377 a
Without	661a	2143 a
Fertiliser		
With (0 kg ha ⁻¹)	604a	2562 a
Without (123.5 kg ha ⁻¹)	556a	1958 a
Plant combination		
Sole bean	1118a	3588 a
bean + maize	366b	932 b
bean + tephrosia,	633 b	NA
bean + maize +tephrosia	204b	NA
Tephrosia green manure		
Sole bean	NA	3864 a
Beans + maize	NA	929 b
Bean + maize + tephrosia	NA	936 b
Bean + tephrosia	NA	3311 a

Discussion

Leguminous trees, shrubs and herbs are widely used in smallholder farms as a means of improving soil fertility to increase the productivity and yields of intercrops, or monocultures of sequential rotational systems. In this trial, the main source of organic fertiliser was tephrosia, supplied as green manure to the second season (long rains) maize and bean crops alone or in combination with inorganic fertiliser. Although the study was undertaken in two consecutive seasons, it was noticeable that significant increase in maize grain yield was realised in the subsequent long rainy season following green manure from intercropping with tephrosia- the improved fallow species. In contrast, sole common bean generally performed better than bean-tephrosia and bean-maize intercrops. Whereas there was significant response of tephrosia (in terms of green manure biomass), it was also interesting to note that there was no significant effect of rhizobial inoculation on bean grain yield. The lack of clear response to inoculation, especially regarding the common bean crop, is likely to be attributed to the occurrence of soil resident common bean-rhizobia, which may be more competitive than the inoculant strain (Makatiani & Odee, 2007). Assessment of indigenous rhizobia using the most probable number method with soils collected prior to the establishment of the trial estimated an indigenous common bean-nodulating rhizobial population of 1.5×10^3 g soil⁻¹. Overall, the highest maize and bean grain yields were higher than the average yields reported for the County (MoALF, 2016) and other regions with similar agro-ecological conditions (e.g. Partey *et al.*, 2017; Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2019). Other benefits of improved tephrosia fallow and intercropping observed in this study included reduced incidence of the parasitic witchweed (*Striga hermonthica*) on maize and general weed suppression.

Table 2. Maize grain yields in different treatments (*Rhizobium* inoculation of companion legume plant-bean and tephrosia, inorganic and organic fertiliser and plant combination) during two consecutive cropping seasons (short and long rains) in Nyabeda, Western Kenya. Means within a treatment factor not followed by the same letter (s) in a column are significantly different at $P=0.05$ according to Fischer least significance difference (LSD); NA, not applicable.

Treatments	Mean Maize yields (Kg ha ⁻¹) Short Rains	Mean Maize yields (Kg ha ⁻¹) Long Rains
Inoculation		
With	4509 a	7583 a
Without	4147 a	8403 a
Fertiliser		
With (0 kg ha ⁻¹)	4646 a	8003 a
Without (123.5 kg ha ⁻¹)	3974 a	7981 a
Plant combination		
sole Maize	4073 a	8292 a
Maize + bean	5700 ab	7543 a
Maize + tephrosia	3704 b	NA
Maize+ bean + tephrosia	3786 b	NA
Tephrosia green manure		
Sole maize	NA	7726 ab
Beans + maize	NA	6966 b
Beans + maize + tephrosia	NA	8235 ab
Maize + tephrosia	NA	8593 ab
Maize (in short rains sole tephrosia plots)	NA	8772 a

The study showed variable bean and maize grain yield production depending on the planting combinations. The efficiency of intercropping over sole cropping will be compared using the land equivalent ratio (LER) method (Willey & Rao, 1980). Further work is also being undertaken to quantify biological nitrogen fixation and the amount of N applied through the tephrosia green manure and stover residues, and N available to the subsequent maize and bean crops to provide further insights for appropriate management of the improved fallow and intercropping to optimise grain yield production. We recommend that smallholder farmers use both simultaneous and sequential tephrosia fallow systems in consecutive seasons.

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